

Landscape overview for the EOSC Federation Semantic Interoperability in 2025

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Executive Summary

Semantic Interoperability is important for realizing the vision of the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC). It ensures that digital objects, such as datasets and publications, are understood in the same intended meaning by both humans and machines across different systems and research communities – a concept summarized as **what is sent is what is understood**. The ability to consistently understand heterogeneous data is fundamental to successfully implementing the FAIR Principles (Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, Reusability) and increase the availability of FAIR data and services for research assets.

This deliverable, mandated by the EOSC Association and written by its Task Force for Technical and Semantic Interoperability, provides an update on the practical implementation of semantic interoperability within the EOSC ecosystem. It builds upon the initial conceptualization of the EOSC Interoperability Framework (EOSC-IF) and the previous recommendations from the Semantic Interoperability Task Force of the EOSC Association.

The deliverable specifically investigates the practical experiences, needs, and requirements of European scientists involved in EOSC projects, national nodes, and thematic nodes. Through a targeted survey, it has identified specific Semantic Artefacts (e.g., vocabularies, ontologies) and corresponding Catalogues to store, publish, and reuse them. The deliverable is written for the EOSC Association, the persons participating in the build-up phase of the EOSC Federation, and all those eager to learn about the state of the art on semantic interoperability in EOSC.

By implementing and standardizing Semantic Interoperability, the EOSC ecosystem is poised to achieve significant benefits: enhanced data and metadata integration, better data reuse and citation accuracy, and the essential preparation of scientific data for Machine Learning/Artificial Intelligence (ML/AI) applications. A concrete example of this is the harmonization of diverse national transportation networks representations across Europe under the INSPIRE directive,¹¹ demonstrating how common semantic artefacts enable effective cross-border data integration.

This document details the state of the art of current semantic interoperability in the EOSC Ecosystem.

- Part 1 reviews the existing foundational recommendations, particularly those published in the sub-group's previous document, *Developing and implementing the semantic interoperability recommendations of the EOSC Interoperability Framework*¹².

¹¹ INSPIRE Directive: https://knowledge-base.inspire.ec.europa.eu/overview_en (last accessed 16/03/2026)

¹² Nyberg Åkerström et al. Developing and implementing the semantic interoperability recommendations of the EOSC Interoperability Framework, <https://zenodo.org/records/10843882> (last accessed 27/12/2025)

- Part 2 presents the results of a survey and direct feedback from EOSC projects and thematic and national Nodes of the EOSC Federation. This section focuses on the practical impact and community perception of Semantic Interoperability, cataloging the specific Semantic Artefacts and Catalogues in use.
- Part 3 provides a specific focus on the intersection of semantic interoperability and the needs arising from the secure, federated ecosystems known as Data Spaces.

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Acronyms

- **AAI:** Authentication and Authorisation Infrastructure. A framework that enables the secure exchange of user identity and access rights
- **AI:** Artificial Intelligence. Systems capable of performing tasks that normally require human intelligence
- **API:** Application Programming Interface. A set of rules and protocols for building and interacting with software applications
- **CDIF:** Cross-Domain Interoperability Framework. A set of recommendations based on domain-neutral standards to support FAIR core functions. *Reference:* [CODATA CDIF](#)
- **DCAT / DCAT-AP:** Data Catalog Vocabulary / Application Profile. A W3C standard and its European profile used for describing data catalogues and datasets to improve discovery. *Reference:* [W3C DCAT](#) / [SEMIC DCAT-AP](#)
- **DDI-CDI:** Data Documentation Initiative – Cross-Domain Integration. A standard designed to facilitate the integration of data across different disciplines
- **DMP:** Data Management Plan. A formal document outlining how research data is handled during and after a project
- **DOI:** Digital Object Identifier. A persistent identifier used to uniquely identify objects such as journal articles or datasets
- **DSGA:** Data Space Governance Authority, the entity responsible for the governance of a data space
- **DSSC:** Data Spaces Support Centre supporting the deployment of the common European data spaces
- **EIF:** European Interoperability Framework. A set of recommendations for public administrations on how to improve the interoperability of their information systems
- **EIRA:** European Interoperability Reference Architecture. A reference architecture focused on the interoperability of public services
- **EMMO:** European Materials Modelling Ontology. A domain-specific ontology for materials science
- **ENVO:** Environmental Ontology. A community-led ontology for representing environmental entities
- **EOSC:** European Open Science Cloud. A European initiative to develop a federated infrastructure for research data
- **EOSC-A:** EOSC Association.
- **EOSC-IF:** EOSC Interoperability Framework. A framework defining the principles for achieving interoperability within EOSC
- **EOSC SI:** EOSC Semantic Interoperability
- **EOSC TI:** EOSC Technical Interoperability

- **FAIR:** Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reusability. A set of principles to ensure research data is discoverable and usable
- **FC4E:** FAIR Core for EOSC. A project developing the core technical components for a FAIR-compliant EOSC
- **FDO:** FAIR Digital Object. A digital entity that encapsulates data and metadata to satisfy FAIR principles
- **GCMD:** Global Change Master Directory. A comprehensive directory of Earth science data sets and services
- **JSON-LD:** JavaScript Object Notation for Linked Data. A method of encoding Linked Data using JSON
- **LOV:** Linked Open Vocabularies. A catalogue for discovering and reusing existing vocabularies on the web
- **ML:** Machine Learning. A field of AI that focuses on the use of data and algorithms to imitate the way humans learn
- **maDMP:** Machine-actionable Data Management Plan. A DMP that can be read and processed by computers
- **NFDI:** Nationale Forschungsdateninfrastruktur. The German national research data infrastructure
- **NVS:** NERC Vocabulary Server. A service providing access to controlled vocabularies for the marine and environmental sciences
- **ODRL:** Open Digital Rights Language. A policy language for expressing rights and permissions in a digital environment. *Reference:* [W3C ODRL](#)
- **ORCID:** Open Researcher and Contributor ID. A unique, persistent identifier for researchers
- **OWL:** Web Ontology Language. A semantic web language designed to represent complex knowledge about things and their relations
- **PID:** Persistent Identifier. A long-lasting reference to a digital resource
- **PROV-O:** The PROV Ontology. A W3C standard for representing provenance (the history of a digital object)
- **RDF:** Resource Description Framework. A standard model for data interchange on the web
- **ROR:** Research Organization Registry. A community-led registry of open identifiers for research organisations
- **SA:** Semantic Artefact. A machine-actionable formalisation of a conceptualisation (e.g., ontology, vocabulary)
- **SAC:** Semantic Artefact Catalogue. A system for the storage and discovery of semantic artefacts
- **SAGE:** the Green Deal Data Space

- **SBO:** Semantic Business Object. An information unit with technical significance used to describe FAIR Digital Objects
- **SEMAF:** Semantic Mapping Framework
- **SEMIC:** Semantic Interoperability Centre Europe. A community supporting the exchange of semantic assets
- **SHACL:** Shapes Constraint Language. A language for validating RDF graphs against a set of conditions. *Reference:* [W3C SHACL](#)
- **SIMPL:** the Smart Middleware Platform, an open source, secure middleware that supports data access and interoperability in European data initiatives.
- **SIP:** Semantic Interoperability Profile. A specification for achieving semantic alignment within a specific context
- **SKOS:** Simple Knowledge Organization System. A standard for representing thesauri, taxonomies, and other controlled vocabularies
- **SOSA:** Sensor, Observation, Sample, and Actuator. An ontology for describing sensors and their observations
- **SSSOM:** Simple Standard for Sharing Ontology Mappings. A standard format for sharing mapping sets between ontologies
- **URI:** Uniform Resource Identifier. A string of characters that unambiguously identifies a particular resource
- **XML:** Extensible Markup Language. A markup language used for storing and transporting data

Introduction

Following earlier EOSC Interoperability Framework guidelines, this document provides an update from the EOSC Association Task Force on the practical and legal state of semantic interoperability.¹³

Semantic interoperability is essential to ensure that the concepts used in data and their descriptions are consistently understood by all users, both humans and machines, across different systems, disciplines and research communities. It plays a central role in making the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) Federation a reality by ensuring that digital objects, such as datasets, publications and software, carry the same intended meaning for everyone involved. This is based on the principle that 'what is sent is what is understood', meaning that the precise intent and context of digital objects are preserved and interpreted consistently by both humans and machines. Achieving this level of shared understanding requires implementing semantic interoperability at both the data and metadata levels.

By harmonising and standardising semantic interoperability practices, the EOSC ecosystem aims to achieve tangible benefits: improved data reuse, more robust data and metadata integration across disciplines, and enhanced readiness of scientific data for Machine Learning (ML) and Artificial Intelligence (AI) applications. A consistent approach to semantic interoperability is a technical requirement and a key enabler of open and FAIR science. It fosters trust, transparency and collaboration within and beyond the EOSC community.

This document aims to support the EOSC Association in strengthening and extending the EOSC Interoperability Framework (EOSC-IF) by integrating the progress made in the EOSC Federation, Task Forces, Projects, Candidate Nodes, and European Data Spaces. The follow-up deliverable (2nd deliverable) will provide practical recommendations for data and metadata providers as well as repository and infrastructure administrators, to enhance their semantic alignment efforts and contribute effectively to the broader EOSC landscape.

The main objective of this document is to present an overview of the current status of Semantic Artefact(e.g., vocabularies, ontologies, metadata schemas) usage and the practical implementations of semantic interoperability within the EOSC ecosystem. Building upon the foundational work of the EOSC-IF and earlier recommendations from the EOSC-A Semantic Interoperability sub-group Task Force (see footnote 12), it also synthesizes knowledge and practices gathered through a targeted survey and from nodes. This survey documents the

¹³ Corcho, Oscar, Eriksson, Magnus, Kurowski, Krzysztof, Ojsteršek, Milan, Choirat, Christine, van de Sanden, Mark, & Coppens, Frederik. (2021). EOSC interoperability framework. Digital library of University of Maribor. <https://dk.um.si/lzpisGradiva.php?id=80597> (last accessed 16/03/2026)

experiences, needs, and requirements of European scientists engaged in EOSC projects, national and thematic nodes, while identifying the Semantic Artefacts (SA) and associated Semantic Artefact Catalogues (SAC) used for their storage, publication, and reuse.

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1. Previous Recommendations for Semantic Interoperability

The EOSC Interoperability Framework (EOSC-IF) builds directly on the principles and concepts of the European Interoperability Framework (EIF) and its European Interoperability Reference Architecture (EIRA), which provides a generic model for achieving interoperability across public administrations in Europe. While EIF and EIRA define four interoperability layers (i.e. legal, organisational, semantic and technical) and generic building blocks, including a semantic view, the EOSC-IF tailors these ideas to the specific needs of the European Open Science Cloud. In particular, the EOSC-IF extends the EIRA semantic interoperability view by introducing FAIR Digital Objects as the atomic units for representing any kind of resource in EOSC, by organising the semantic layer into semantic governance content (agreements, policies, principles) and Semantic Functional Content: catalogues, repositories, and services that implement these agreements.

Figure 1: Semantic view of the Reference Architecture presented in the EOSC-IF

Within this semantic view, FAIR Digital Objects^{14,15,16} are one way to encapsulate metadata and other semantic descriptions, that was aimed in the previous recommendation. Their meaning depends on Semantic Business Objects (SBO) and supporting semantic artefacts. Semantic Business Objects represent key domain concepts (such as datasets, services, or workflows) and provide the conceptual anchors for data models, metadata frameworks, and identifier schemes. Around them, the EOSC-IF defines components such as a Metadata Catalogue, a Semantic Artefact Catalogue, and a Mapping Repository, which together enable the discovery, governance, and alignment of semantic artefacts..

In the deliverable published by the initial EOSC Association Semantic Interoperability Task Force (see footnote 12), four recommendations areas were identified to help align the strategic and operational priorities of projects and individuals developing and implementing interoperability solutions for EOSC. For this overview a subset of EOSC-IF terms that are most relevant for semantic interoperability practices and introduce some additional, EOSC-specific concepts was selected.

Figure 2: Overview of the subset of EOSC-IF terms: In green, newly introduced terms (Definitions see Appendix A) and how they are related.

¹⁴ S. Collins, F. Genova, N. Harrower, S. Hodson, S. Jones, L. Laaksonen, D. Mietchen, R. Petrauskaitė, P. Wittenburg, Final Report and Action Plan from the European Commission Expert Group on FAIR Data, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/1524> (last accessed 27/12/2025)

¹⁵ FAIR Digital Objects, nfdi4phys, <https://nfdi4phys.de/fdo/> (last accessed 27/12/2025)

¹⁶ Soiland-Reyes, S., Goble, C., & Groth, P. (2023). Evaluating FAIR Digital Object and Linked Data as distributed object systems. <https://doi.org/10.48550/ARXIV.2306.07436> (last accessed 27/12/2025)

Based on these previous recommendations and actions, this chapter reflects the existing context of semantic interoperability within the EOSC ecosystem..

The four recommendation areas and their proposed actions are intended to strengthen the implementation, enable support and reuse, and promote alignment across the different data spaces. This chapter distills the most important aspects of these recommendations, drawing on relevant literature and prior outputs to underscore their significance and outline potential pathways forward.

1.1. EOSC-IF Semantic Alignment in Practical Implementations

Aligning implementations with a future reference architecture would provide a shared frame of reference, and would enable stakeholders to exchange knowledge, converge on common practices, and develop shared semantic solutions that are foundational to interoperability. The convergence on terminology and alignment with the pan-European data spaces (e.g., GAIA-X¹⁷, Interoperable Europe¹⁸, Common European Data Spaces¹⁹) is not only timely but essential for sustainability. As David et al.²⁰ emphasised, harmonisation across projects requires more than documentation; it depends on collaborative governance and incentives. Early work on federated systems (Sheth & Larson²¹) remains relevant, underscoring the need for frameworks that support autonomous yet interoperable components. Consolidating implementation resources and architectural views will strengthen semantic coherence within the EOSC Federation and across the EOSC nodes.

Previous Recommendations and Actions

- Create and maintain a single, authoritative resource that brings together all EOSC-IF implementation efforts, to put the EOSC-IF into practice.²²
- Continue bringing experts together to raise awareness and align on good practices shared through EOSC-IF.
- EOSC Nodes should adopt interoperable solutions and align architectures with the

¹⁷ GAIA-X - <http://gaia-x.eu> (last accessed 27/12/2025)

¹⁸ Interoperable Europe - <http://interoperable-europe.ec.europa.eu/interoperable-europe> (last accessed 27/12/2025)

¹⁹ European Common Data Spaces - <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/data-spaces> (last accessed 27/12/2025)

²⁰ David, R. et al. (2023). Converging on a Semantic Interoperability Framework for the European Data Space. [DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.8042997](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8042997) (last accessed 27/12/2025)

²¹ Sheth, A. and Larson, J. (1990), Federated Database Systems for Managing Distributed, Heterogeneous, and Autonomous Databases. ACM Computing Surveys, 22, 183-236. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1145/96602.96604> (last accessed 27/12/2025)

²² There are ongoing efforts to put EOSC-IF into practice. E.g. the EOSC Interoperability Registry v 1.0, currently run within the EOSC EU Node Resource Hub. Additionally the updated Interoperability Guidelines are under development mainly within the projects EOSC-Beyond and EOSC United.

EOSC-IF.

- Use the semantic aspects of the EOSC-IF to guide and evaluate mediation across EOSC Nodes and stakeholders.

1.2. The Research Process Perspective

Introducing a research process lens into the EOSC-IF is a commendable shift towards usability and relevance. Demonstrators, case studies, and curated use cases can validate the EOSC-IF's value proposition to researchers, funders, and service providers. Daga et al.²³ and Nyberg Åkerström & Maccallum²⁴ highlight how process documentation and targeted case studies enhance user engagement and uptake. Incorporating resources such as the FAIR Cookbook²⁵ and the Cross-Domain Interoperability Framework (CDIF) (CODATA²⁶, Gregory, A. et al.²⁷), strengthens support for implementing FAIR data by offering reusable and standard based components, which in turn lower the barriers for reusing data across domains. In parallel, engaging with initiatives like Interoperable Europe and SEMIC²⁸ extends the EOSC's reach and increases its alignment with wider digital transformation goals across public and academic sectors.

Previous Recommendations and Action

- Add a framework and curated examples of semantic interoperability use cases to the EOSC-IF.
- Offer incentives and support for stakeholders to share and validate common use cases (e.g. SIP survey, FAIR Cookbook).
- Engage with external communities on similar interoperability challenges, including SEMIC, CDIF and standardisation bodies.
- Catalogue existing EOSC and community recommendations linked to common use cases and EOSC-IF elements (e.g. FAIRsFAIR²⁹, FAIR Cookbook, CDIF)

²³ Daga, E., Daquino, M., Fournier-S'niehotta, R., Guillotel-Nothmann, C., & Scharnhorst, A. (2023). Documenting the research process. Opportunities and challenges for Bibliometrics and Information Retrieval. <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.8249512> (last accessed 27/12/2025)

²⁴ Nyberg Åkerström & Maccallum (2023), Case studies and use cases as means of effectively demonstrating value and engaging stakeholders. <https://doi.org/10.17044/sciifelab.21542313> (last accessed 27/12/2025)

²⁵ FAIR Cookbook - <https://www.nature.com/articles/s41597-023-02166-3> (last accessed 27/12/2025)

²⁶ CODATA (2024). Committee on Data of the ISC: CDIF. <https://codata.org/initiatives/making-data-work/cdif/> (last accessed 27/12/2025)

²⁷ Gregory, A. et al. (2024). WorldFAIR (D2.3) Cross-Domain Interoperability Framework (CDIF) (Report Synthesising Recommendations for Disciplines and Cross-Disciplinary Research Areas): DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.11236871](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11236871) (last accessed 27/12/2025), Corcho, O. et al. (2024a). A Maturity Model for Catalogues of Semantic Artefacts. arXiv:2305.06746 or published version DOI:[10.1038/s41597-024-03185-4](https://doi.org/10.1038/s41597-024-03185-4) (last accessed 27/12/2025)

²⁸ SEMIC - <https://interoperable-europe.ec.europa.eu/collection/semic-support-centre> (last accessed 27/12/2025)

²⁹ Since the recommendation publication, some follow-up projects have started, e.g. FAIR IMPACT.

1.3. Expanding Semantic Business Objects to Include Mappings and Crosswalks

Recognising mappings and crosswalks as formal Semantic Business Objects fills a gap in the EOSC-IF. These artefacts enable interoperability across diverse metadata schemas and domain vocabularies and ontologies. Their FAIRness and reuse, however, depend on shared standards and governance mechanisms. The maturity of existing work on mappings, such as the FAIR-IMPACT³⁰ mapping guidelines and SSSOM³¹, provides a solid starting point. Future progress will require establishing lifecycle management processes, metadata consistency, and supporting tools to avoid redundancy and fragmentation.

Previous Recommendations and Action

- Standardise formats (e.g. building on SSSOM) to describe semantic relationships like mappings and crosswalks to support data integration.
- Make mappings across EOSC projects, crosswalks FAIR by documenting and sharing them using FAIR-IMPACT guidance. Furthermore, use mapping and crosswalk registries as for example developed through the FAIRCORE4EOSC³² project.
- Define best practices for defining reliable metadata to support semantic mediation.
- Set up a governance structure to manage the lifecycle of mappings and crosswalks, ensuring quality and avoiding duplication.

1.4. Elevating Semantic Artefact Catalogues as Core Infrastructure

Semantic artefact catalogues are recognised in the EOSC-IF's long-term vision as essential infrastructure for managing and governing controlled vocabularies and ontologies. A maturity model proposed by Corcho et al.^{33,34} (2024a, 2024b) offers concrete criteria, such as machine-actionability, cross-domain coverage, and metadata richness, for systematically

³⁰ FAIR-IMPACT, D4.5 - Guidelines and methodology to create, document and share mappings and crosswalks
DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.15111167 (last accessed 16/02/2026)

³¹ Simple Standard for Sharing Ontological Mappings (SSSOM) - <https://mapping-commons.github.io/sssom/> (last accessed 27/12/2025)

³² FAIRCORE4EOSC -
<https://faircore4eosc.eu/eosc-core-components/metadata-schema-and-crosswalk-registry-mscr> (last accessed 27/12/2025)

³³ Corcho, O. et al. (2024a). A Maturity Model for Catalogues of Semantic Artefacts. arXiv:2305.06746 or published version DOI:[10.1038/s41597-024-03185-4](https://doi.org/10.1038/s41597-024-03185-4) (last accessed 27/12/2025)

³⁴ Corcho, O. et al. (2024b). Catalogues of Semantic Artefacts—Maturity Dimensions and Features. DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.10625936](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10625936) (last accessed 27/12/2025)

evaluating and improving these services, while Keith and Broeder³⁵ proposed common metadata set across EOSC Nodes to support coherent FAIR implementation.

FAIR-IMPACT (Poveda-Villalón et al.³⁶) translated this into practice by applying FAIR principles across the semantic artefact lifecycle, from design, to publication, to assessment and use in data repositories, and by advancing technical interoperability via a common MOD-API³⁷ and a OntoPortal-based federation that enables unified, programmatic access and cross-portal discovery. To fully realise this potential, Semantic Artefact Catalogues must be embedded into everyday research workflows. Therefore, these Catalogues need to be firmly integrated within the EOSC Federation to enable both domain-specific and cross-domain semantic alignment.

Previous Recommendations and Action

- Develop and align maturity models for semantic artefact catalogues with other EOSC recommendations.
- Create strategies to improve catalogue quality, reliability, machine-actionability, and cross-domain use. (FC4E³⁸)
- Facilitate easier registration, maintenance, and curation of semantic artefacts, including supported workflows for metadata harmonisation and FAIRness assessment.
- Encourage the use of existing domain and cross-domain catalogues and prevent duplication of SAC infrastructures.
- Adopt a common MOD- and DCAT-based metadata standard for describing semantic artefacts and their catalogues across all EOSC Nodes.
- Promote the implementation of the shared MOD-API and federation mechanism (e.g. OntoPortal federation, API GWs), and support the development of reusable connectors between SACs and data repositories, allowing SACs to function as core elements supporting semantic interoperability within the EOSC Federation.

1.5. Summary

The 2024 EOSC SI recommendations show a mature understanding of semantic interoperability as a socio-technical, multi-layered challenge. Together, the focus on aligning implementations with the EOSC-IF semantic view, promoting the FAIR Digital Object model, adding a research process perspective, elevating mappings and crosswalks, and treating Semantic Artefact

³⁵ Keith, J., & Broeder, D. (2024). EOSCfuture Metadata Working Group Recommendations. [DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.10497034](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10497034) (last accessed 27/12/2025)

³⁶ Poveda-Villalón et al. (2025). D4.2: FAIR semantic artefact lifecycle from engineering, to sharing. <https://zenodo.org/records/14643279> (last accessed 27/12/2025)

³⁷ MOD-API - <https://github.com/FAIR-IMPACT/MOD-API> (last accessed 27/12/2025)

³⁸ FAIRCORE4EOSC - <https://faircore4eosc.eu/> (last accessed 27/12/2025)

Catalogues as core infrastructure components to form a coherent roadmap rather than a collection of isolated actions. The key message is that architecture, semantics, and practice must be tightly coupled and systematically embedded in the EOSC Federation and scientific workflows. Another look at the previous recommendations brings the: FAIR-IMPACT project.³⁹

At the same time, the recommendations underline that success depends on more than technical solutions. Community mobilisation, sustainable governance, and clear incentives are essential to ensure that semantic artefacts, mappings, catalogues, and use cases are created, curated, and reused as shared public goods. By grounding its architecture in real-world use cases, aligning with wider initiatives such as GAIA-X, Interoperable Europe and SEMIC, and demonstrating tangible value for stakeholders, moves EOSC closer to realising a truly FAIR, federated, and interoperable research ecosystem.

³⁹ Jonquet, C., et al. (2024). FAIR-IMPACT project response to "DRAFT: Developing and implementing the semantic interoperability recommendations of the EOSC Interoperability Framework" (Verze V1). Zenodo.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10874897> (last accessed 16/03/2026)

2. Current status of Semantic Interoperability in the EOSC ecosystem

To understand the current landscape and identify where alignment, tooling, and guidance are most needed, a short survey was conducted among EOSC Projects and Nodes. The aim of this chapter was to gather an overview of how semantic interoperability is being considered in practice, which artefacts and catalogues are used or developed, and what challenges and opportunities are emerging. Responses were limited to one per project or node to ensure consolidated input. In addition to the survey, targeted research infrastructures were asked to provide details on handling semantic interoperability.

The following subchapters present the methodology and a summary of the survey that was conducted. Its purpose is to highlight key responses, themes, and insights in a clear and accessible way without going into too much detail leaving space for a future survey to explore Semantic Interoperability during the operational phase of the EOSC Federation. Subchapter [2.4](#) presents examples of semantic interoperability in specific nodes.

2.1. Survey methodology

Survey instrument: A targeted questionnaire was distributed to ongoing and recently completed EOSC projects and EOSC-related initiatives to gather information on their practical experience with semantic interoperability, including the Semantic Artefacts (SAs) and the Semantic Artefact Catalogues (SACs) they use. Because semantic interoperability is also addressed at the level of thematic and national nodes, coordinators of relevant National and Thematic Nodes were likewise invited to complete the survey. All the text in this and following subchapters are literally results from the survey as submitted from the projects and node representatives.

Respondents: The following projects, initiatives and EOSC nodes contributed to this consultation:

- EOSC | Blue-Cloud (<https://blue-cloud.org/>)
- EOSC Node | CERN (<https://eosc.eu/building-the-eosc-federation/eosc-node-cern>)
- CLIMATE-ADAPT4EOSC (<https://climate-adapt4eosc.eu/>)
- DAPHNE4NFDI (Public meta-data catalogue) (<https://www.daphne4nfdi.de/english/>)
- EOSC EU Node (<https://open-science-cloud.ec.europa.eu/>)
- EOSC | LUMEN (<https://lumenproject.eu/>)
- EOSC Node | Slovakia (<https://eosc.eu/building-the-eosc-federation/eosc-node-slovakia>)
- EOSC Observing Partner (incl. EOSC Life, ENVRI-FAIR, Blue Cloud, Ocean & Waters)
- EOSC | FAIR-EASE (<https://fairease.eu/>)

- EOSC | FAIR-IMPACT (<https://fair-impact.eu/>)
- EOSC | FIDELIS (<https://eden-fidelis.eu/>)
- Materials Commons 4 Europe (submitted) (<https://materialscommons4.eu/>)
- EOSC Node | Germany (<https://eosc.eu/building-the-eosc-federation/eosc-node-germany>)
- OPAL (OSCARS Cascading Grant) (<https://oscars-project.eu/projects/opal-ontology-portal-astronomy-linked-data>)
- Open Energy Family (https://openenergyplatform.github.io/organisation/family_members/)
- OSTrails (<https://ostrails.eu/>)

Analysis: Responses were aggregated and synthesized to identify common practices, repeated vocabularies, and shared challenges.

Coverage spans: energy, climate, astronomy, materials science, earth sciences, health, marine, mathematics, molecular dynamics, humanities and cross-domain EOSC nodes and infrastructures.

Limitations: The consultation provides an indicative overview, but several constraints should be noted. The sample size was limited and does not fully reflect the diversity of the EOSC activities. Several contributing projects are still in development, which affects the completeness of the information available. It was also challenging to identify the most relevant contacts for semantic interoperability in each project, leading to uneven depth and consistency across responses.

Because many respondents also participated last year in a similar survey, some answers reflect continuity rather than new developments. Consequently, these findings represent illustrative trends and qualitative snapshots of the current landscape, providing a foundation for future, more exhaustive benchmarking.

2.2. Survey findings

This chapter summarises answers from the survey ordered by the questions asked. Each participant was asked to answer the following questions in the context of their project or node:

1. Is Semantic Interoperability taken into consideration within your Project or Node?
2. Semantic Artefacts (SAs): ontologies and vocabularies used or developed?
3. Semantic Artefact Catalogues (SACs): catalogues or vocabulary registries in use or under development?
4. Semantic annotation of data or metadata to enhance FAIRness?
5. Mappings and crosswalks implemented?

6. Standards and specifications adopted?
7. What are the outcomes?
8. Are the outcomes positive?
9. How could the implementation of Semantic Interoperability in EOSC be improved?

Questions 1 and 8 are yes or no questions, other questions are answered as free text. The goal is to give a general understanding on which semantic artefacts are actually used in the projects and nodes and what is the experience. Positiveness of outcomes is self-evaluated. General findings are summarized in the following text, ordered by the questions.

Consideration of Semantic Interoperability

All but one respondent (project or node) confirmed that semantic interoperability is considered.

IS SEMANTIC INTEROPERABILITY TAKEN INTO CONSIDERATION WITHIN YOUR PROJECT OR NODE?

Semantic Artefacts (Ontologies and Vocabularies used or developed)

The following semantic artefacts have been mentioned as being important and are in the focus of development in the projects and nodes.

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Artefact	Existing/ Developed	What it covers (very short)	Where
DCAT family (DCAT / DCAT-AP / DCAT - FE)	Existing	Data catalogue / dataset metadata	Cross-domain EOSC projects
Dublin Core / DataCite / Schema.org	Existing	Generic research/web metadata	Cross-domain
PROV-O	Existing	Provenance	Cross-domain
SKOS / OWL	Existing	Concept schemes / ontology modelling	Cross-domain
CodeMeta	Existing	Software metadata	Software/cross-domain
EMMO	Existing	Materials science ontology	Materials
Open Energy Ontology	Developed	Energy domain semantics	Energy
FIDELIS TRAM	Developed	Trustworthy repo attributes	Repositories ⁴⁰
TRIPLE Ontology	Developed	TRIPLE/LUMEN semantics	Cross-domain
FAIR-IMPACT Semantic Artefact Accessibility	Developed	FAIR semantic/metadata guidelines	Cross-domain ³⁹

Semantic Artefact Catalogues (SACs) in use or under development

The following semantic artefact catalogues are currently in use in projects and/or nodes. This list can provide inspiration for adoption in other projects or nodes.

⁴⁰ This was the answer from the questionnaire, however this is not an artefact.

SAC / Service	Role	Where
LOV	Cross-domain vocabulary discovery/hosting	EOSC / general
OntoPortal family (incl. AgroPortal, EcoPortal, EarthPortal, BiodivPortal)	Portal framework for domain SACs	Agronomy, Astronomy, Earth, Biodiversity, Ecology domains
NVS	Marine SAC	Marine
TIB Terminology Service	Terminology hosting/access	NFDI, materials
SKOSMOS	SKOS vocab publishing	National/EOSC infra ⁴¹

Semantic Annotation of Data or Metadata to Enhance FAIRness

The following common practices or repeated standards for annotation for semantic annotation of data or metadata to enhance FAIRness are currently in use in projects and/or nodes. This list can provide inspiration for adoption in other projects or nodes.

- Common practices:
 - Annotation at dataset and column level.
 - Use of semantic search and JSON-LD/turtle metadata.
 - Annotation via specific services such as marineinfo.org and data.emobon.embrc.eu.
 - Semantic analyser tool to suggest mappings and replace free-text keywords with URIs.
 - Knowledge graphs with semantic annotations.
- Repeated standards for annotation: DCAT,⁴² PROV⁴³, SKOS⁴⁴, Dublin Core⁴⁵, DataCite⁴⁶.

⁴¹ This was the answer from the questionnaire, however this is not a SAC, but instances of SKOSMOS can be used as a service, if it is deployed.

⁴² DCAT 3.0: <https://www.w3.org/TR/vocab-dcat-3/> (last accessed 16/03/2026)

⁴³ PROV-O: <https://www.w3.org/TR/prov-o/> (last accessed 16/03/2026)

⁴⁴ SKOS: <https://www.w3.org/2004/02/skos/> (last accessed 16/03/2026)

⁴⁵ Dublin Core: <https://www.dublincore.org/resources/glossary/ontology/> (last accessed 16/03/2026)

⁴⁶ DataCite: <https://schema.datacite.org/meta/kernel-4.6/> (last accessed 16/03/2026)

Mappings and Crosswalks Implemented

The following mappings and crosswalks are currently in use in projects and/or nodes. This list can provide inspiration for adoption in other projects or nodes.

- Repeated mappings:
 - ISO19115 → DCAT-FE
 - machine actionable Data Management Plans (maDMP) mappings ,
 - Schema.org / CodeMeta mappings,
 - MARC21 → Dublin Core / DataCite,
 - SSSOM (Simple Standard for Sharing Ontological Mappings).
- Crosswalks are widely used to harmonize metadata across repositories and infrastructures.

Standards and Specifications Adopted

The following standards and specifications are currently in use in projects and/or nodes. This list can provide inspiration for adoption in other projects or nodes.

- Most repeated standards and specifications:
 - DCAT / DCAT-AP / DCAT-FE
 - Dublin Core
 - DataCite
 - Schema.org

- PROV-O
- SKOS / OWL
- OAI-PMH
- ISO standards (ISO19115, ISO 5259, ISO 639-2, ISO 690)
- Identifiers: ORCID, DOI, ROR
- Many projects also referenced other standards and vocabularies (e.g., Environmental Ontology (ENVO), Sensor Observation Sample and Actuator (SOSA), European Materials Modelling Ontology (EMMO), I-ADOPT framework, Global Change Master Directory (GCMD) etc).

What are the Outcomes?

The following responses address whether semantic interoperability produces specific **Outcomes**. These replies are summarised here and have not been further interpreted.

- Improved FAIRness of datasets, homogeneous output from multiple repositories,
- Creation of semantic-aware catalogues and knowledge graphs,
- Enhanced data discovery and access services,
- Federative infrastructures for materials science and energy,
- Awareness and convergence of semantic artefacts in astronomy,
- Trust frameworks,
- EOSC EU Node: implementation of interoperability guidelines and AAI federation.⁴⁷
- Creation of the DCAT-FE profile,
- Implementation of Cross-Domain Interoperability Framework (CDIF) use cases.
- Development of semantic search through data buses.

Are the Outcomes Positive?

- Yes: Majority of participants reported positive outcomes. (12 participants)
- Maybe: Some participants are still in early stages. (3 participants)
- Blank: One participant did not answer

⁴⁷ This is not an outcome, it talks about overall interoperability guidelines within the EOSC EU Node

ARE THE OUTCOMES POSITIVE?

Improving the Semantic Interoperability in the EOSC

Experts provided extensive feedback on how to improve Semantic Interoperability within EOSC. The following recommendations were synthesized from the survey:

- Normative Guidance & Coordination:
 - There is a request for **more normative guidance** and a **coordinated, expert-led decision** on recommended thesauri for each discipline.
 - Harmonisation: Experts call for aligning semantic approaches to prevent **bottom-up** fragmentation. A shared European ontological thesaurus or **high-granularity** backbone was suggested.
- Technical Infrastructure:
 - Centralised Registries: Better coordination between Semantic Artefact Catalogues (SACs) is needed.
 - Tooling: Urgent need for converters between standards and SHACL shapes for automatic validation.
 - EOSC EU Node Alignment: Specific requests for the EOSC EU Node to implement **actual semantics** (systematic URI usage instead of free text keywords) and

expose interfaces (OAI-PMH) that support multiple schema profiles (Schema.org, DCAT).

- Support & Funding:
 - Targeted Funding: Calls should mandate specific standards rather than general IT interoperability.
 - Granularity: Future work should address granularity at the variable level (DDI-CDI), access (ODRL), and packaging (RO-Crate).
- Specific Frameworks to follow:
 - Adoption of CDIF (Cross-Domain Interoperability Framework).
 - Alignment with SKG (Scientific Knowledge Graph) Interoperability Framework.

2.3. Survey results summary and interpretation

The consultation reveals a high level of engagement on semantic interoperability, with 94% of responding projects, initiatives and nodes (15 out of 16), reporting largely positive outcomes, particularly in terms of improved data discovery and FAIRness. At the same time, the expert responses make clear that current efforts remain fragmented and often shallow, driven largely **bottom-up at project level**. A strong, shared consensus emerges that semantic interoperability in EOSC must move beyond isolated implementations toward **coordinated, standards-based and operationally embedded semantics**. Experts emphasise systematic use of machine-actionable metadata (e.g. JSON-LD, RDF/Turtle), persistent identifiers instead of free text keywords, and shared profiles built on widely adopted vocabularies and frameworks such as DCAT, PROV, SOSA, Schema.org, ODRL, RO-Crate, CDIF and SHACL. Interoperability is understood as a cross-cutting concern that must span from discovery to variable-level semantics, access and governance conditions, provenance, and packaging, supported by mappings, crosswalks, validation shapes, semantic registries and analysis tools. Survey participants repeatedly call for **stronger coordination and normative guidance**: harmonising semantic approaches across communities, aligning more closely with the EOSC Federation of nodes and interoperability frameworks, operating semantic artefact registries, and avoiding siloed development. Many respondents also stress the need for incentives, targeted funding and, where appropriate, **EOSC endorsed community recommendations** to drive adoption. The most used vocabularies, catalogues and mappings are:

- DCAT, Dublin Core, DataCite, Schema.org, PROV-O, SKOS, OWL are the most repeated vocabularies/standards.
- NVS, OntoPortal/AgroPortal/EarthPortal/EcoPortal/BiodivPortal, LOV, TIB Terminology Service are the most referenced catalogues.

- ISO19115 → DCAT mappings, maDMP mappings, MARC21 → Dublin Core/DataCite crosswalks are the most common mappings/ crosswalks implemented.
- Projects consistently highlight the need for harmonization, normative guidance, URI-based semantics, and cross-domain frameworks to strengthen EOSC-wide interoperability.

The combined feedback indicates that semantic interoperability in EOSC will only scale if technical solutions are matched with **sustainable governance and targeted funding**. By aligning with cross-domain frameworks and the evolving requirements of European Data Spaces, EOSC can transition from a collection of federated nodes into a truly interoperable research environment where **what is sent is what is understood**.

2.4. Examples of semantic interoperability practices in EOSC

In addition to the survey, targeted research infrastructures were asked to provide details on handling semantic interoperability. Four respondents have described their experience and approach as outlined below.

German Research Data Infrastructure (NFDI)

Next to the *German EOSC node*, the base services of the *German Research Data Infrastructure* (Base4NFDI⁴⁸) joint initiative is developing several services and infrastructures for semantic interoperability: the Terminology Service, the Knowledge Graph and the Persistent Identifier (PID) service. All of these services are developed community driven and bottom up by scientists.

A Knowledge Graph Infrastructure is built by the KGI4NFDI⁴⁹ subproject. It will provide a knowledge graph registry to decentralised, domain specific knowledge graphs and expert knowledge to recommend, standardise and interoperate knowledge graphs.

Terminology Services for NFDI (TS4NFDI⁵⁰) is a cross-domain service for the provision, curation, development, harmonization, and mapping of terminologies. It aims to facilitate consensus-building and interoperability of services across disciplines to achieve a shared knowledge representation and knowledge engineering framework. The service seeks to integrate and converge individual solutions into a standardized, interoperable, and sustainable service suite with a Service Wrapper, API Gateway, mapping service, and reusable GUI widgets.

⁴⁸ Base4NFDI - <https://base4nfdi.de/> (last accessed 27/12/2025)

⁴⁹ KGI4NFDI - <https://kqi.services.base4nfdi.de/> (last accessed 27/12/2025)

⁵⁰ TS4NFDI - <https://terminology.services.base4nfdi.de/> (last accessed 27/12/2025)

A PID coordination hub (PID4NFDI⁵¹) is planned to manage persistent identifiers of many types in a centralised way. Persistent Identifiers can be used to persistently identify datasets, samples, etc., but also semantic artefacts, like vocabularies, taxonomies and ontologies - or even concepts/classes in these ontologies.

Next to the Base4NFDI services a NFDI wide mid-level ontology is developed (Ontology for NFDI⁵²). This ontology can be used to describe the data generation process and provenance of research data. Very related is also the development of a base DCAT-AP metadata schema for characterising metadata of research data (DCAT-AP-plus⁵³): it offers a modular schema approach leveraging the LinkML⁵⁴ data schema description framework.

The HUN-REN Data Repository Platform (HUN-REN ARP) in Hungary

The HUN-REN Data Repository Platform⁵⁵ is a repository infrastructure service that supports the continuous and long-term research data management of the entire HUN-REN research network. The key component is the ARP Data Repository (based on Dataverse) with enhanced support for rich and FAIR metadata and RO-Crate dataset packaging. The ARP Schema Registry⁵⁶ (based on CEDAR⁵⁷) component offers visual and collaborative schema editing, strengthened by a coupled OntoPortal instance as semantic artefact catalog. The ARP RO-Crate Manager (AROMA) is integrated into the ARP Data Repository⁵⁸ and enables researchers to use the published schemas from the registry in their metadata entries on both dataset and file level.

Metadata and their schemas are collected together in the central ARP Knowledge Graph⁵⁹ which also serves as a Federated Search component for several repositories containing datasets of Hungarian origin. Other data repositories are harvested using the OAI-PMH protocol with their most suitable metadata export format. These metadata are also converted to RDF, so finally all metadata of these research datasets are available in the Jena⁶⁰ database of the knowledge graph.

Data Terra

⁵¹ PID4NFDI - <https://pid.services.base4nfdi.de/> (last accessed 27/12/2025)

⁵² Ontology for NFDI - <https://ise-fizkarlsruhe.github.io/nfdicore/> (last accessed 27/12/2025)

⁵³ DCAT-AP metadata schema for research data - <https://github.com/nfdi-de/dcat-ap-plus> (last accessed 27/12/2025)

⁵⁴ LinkML data schema - <http://linkml.org> (last accessed 27/12/2025)

⁵⁵ HUN-REN Data Repository Platform - <https://researchdata.hu/en/our-activities> (last accessed 27/12/2025)

⁵⁶ ARP Schema Registry - <https://schema.researchdata.hu/> (last accessed 27/12/2025)

⁵⁷ CEDAR schema registry - <https://metadatacenter.org/happenings/news/cedar-hungary-arp-integration/> (last accessed 27/12/2025)

⁵⁸ ARP Data Repository - <https://schema.researchdata.hu/> (last accessed 27/12/2025)

⁵⁹ ARP Knowledge Graph - <https://search.researchdata.hu/> (last accessed 27/12/2025)

⁶⁰ Apache Jena - <https://jena.apache.org/> (last accessed 27/12/2025)

Semantic interoperability in the Data Terra EOSC Node is supported by a comprehensive and evolving framework that integrates multidisciplinary ontologies, standardised metadata schemas, and interconnected semantic resources. Since 2019, efforts have focused (i) on developing a terminological registry, the Terra Vocabulary registry⁶¹ that hosts controlled vocabularies for Earth and environmental sciences, (ii) on developing a multidisciplinary application profile⁶² combining DCAT and SOSA ontologies to meet the requirements of earth and life sciences communities, and (iii) by implementing a semantic artefact catalogue for the Earth Sciences, the EarthPortal⁶³.

Based on these achievements, a discovery system that harvests, transforms and enriches metadata from major French environmental data catalogues has been implemented. The Terra Vocabulary⁶⁴ registry serves as a terminological backbone to support consistent metadata description and FAIR data management in this discovery platform. Within the EOSC FAIR-IMPACT project, a connector⁶⁵ has been implemented between the French National Earth & Environment data repository EaSy Data⁶⁶ and EarthPortal to enhance metadata FAIRness through automatic alignment and enriched semantic discovery. All metadata schemas of these services are based on ISO 19115-3 and the DCAT-AP profile to ensure wide compatibility. Data Terra also actively contributes to OGC workgroups to integrate DCAT and SOSA standards, addressing a key gap in semantic modelling for environmental data.

These combined efforts establish a well-structured, multidisciplinary semantic infrastructure that enhances data sharing, discovery, and interoperability across earth and environmental sciences in the Data Terra EOSC Node.

Digital Twin of the Ocean (DTO)

Semantic interoperability in the Digital Twin of the Ocean EOSC Node is achieved through a strategy of harmonisation that aligns heterogeneous marine data infrastructures (BDIs) into a common framework by combining metadata brokerage, controlled vocabularies, and linked data technologies.

⁶¹ Terra Vocabulary registry - https://terra-vocabulary.org/ncl/_FAIR-Incubator (last accessed 27/12/2025)

⁶² Application profile - https://qitlab.in2p3.fr/gaia-data/wp3-services/vocabulaires/dataterra_ap/dataterra_geodcatap (last accessed 27/12/2025)

⁶³ EarthPortal - <https://Earthportal.eu> (last accessed 27/12/2025)

⁶⁴ Terra Vocabulary - https://earthportal.eu/ontologies?groups=DATA_TERRA&search=TERRA (last accessed 27/12/2025)

⁶⁵ FAIR-IMPACT connector - <https://fair-impact.eu/use-cases/enhance-semantic-functionally-national-earth-environmental-data-repository-integrating-it> (last accessed 27/12/2025)

⁶⁶ EaSy Data - <https://www.easydata.earth> (last accessed 27/12/2025)

The Discovery and Access Broker (DAB) harmonises metadata from diverse sources using ISO 19115/19139⁶⁷ standards and XML schemas, ensuring a shared baseline for discovery. The DAB is complemented by the semantic analyser,⁶⁸ which analyses list of terms, datasets and metadata records and provides mappings between free text and semantic artefacts. Those are mappings of discipline-specific metadata (chemistry, biology, genomics, Argo floats, carbon data) to Blue-Cloud ⁶⁹core elements, supported by controlled vocabularies from initiatives such as SeaDataNet/NVS⁷⁰, OBIS/EurOBIS⁷¹, ICOS⁷², and ELIXIR-ENA⁷³.

To strengthen semantic consistency, the shared baseline for harmonisation ISO19115 is then converted to a DCAT profile using RDF triples, and SPARQL enabling machine-actionable semantics across infrastructures. Main vocabularies and standards used are DCAT, PROV, SOSA, NVS, World Register of Marine Species (WoRMS)⁷⁴, DarwinCore⁷⁵ etc.

⁶⁷ ISO 19115/ISO 19139 - <https://www.iso.org/standard/53798.html> / <https://www.iso.org/standard/53798.html> - (last accessed 27/12/2025)

⁶⁸ Semantic Analyser - <https://semantics.bodc.ac.uk/> (last accessed 27/12/2025)

⁶⁹ Blue Cloud: <https://blue-cloud.org/> (last access 16/03/2026)

⁷⁰ SeaDataNet/NVS - <https://www.seadatanet.org/Standards/Common-Vocabularies> (last accessed 27/12/2025)

⁷¹ OBIS/EurOBIS - <https://eurobis.org/obis> (last accessed 27/12/2025)

⁷² ICOS - <https://www.icos-otc.org/> (last accessed 27/12/2025)

⁷³ ELIXIR-ENA - <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/> (last accessed 27/12/2025)

⁷⁴ World Register of Marine Species (WoRMS) - <https://www.marinespecies.org/> (last accessed 27/12/2025)

⁷⁵ Darwin Core - <https://dwc.tdwg.org/> (last accessed 27/12/2025)

3. Data Spaces and Interoperability – arising issues

As EOSC is considered as the Data Space for research, we have to understand the interoperability between EOSC and other Data Spaces. The ability to use data from other Data Spaces is a natural extension of possibilities of the EOSC Federation. The ability to find new data sets in several scientific domains is closely linked to overall semantic interoperability, thus we are devoting this chapter about Data Spaces - EOSC connection to this deliverable. Because we are talking about the Data Spaces and Interoperability for the first time, the chapter is defining some of the concepts for better understanding.

Interoperability in the Data Spaces ecosystem can be understood on several levels:

- 1) Governance (legal and organisational) interoperability within and between data spaces,
- 2) Semantic interoperability at the metadata layer, and
- 3) Semantic interoperability at the data layer.

As the designated Common European Data Space for Research, EOSC must navigate these interoperability layers to comply with the EU Data Act⁷⁶ (art. 33, page 59), which mandates clear asset descriptions to facilitate secure discovery and authorised use.

3.1. Governance Interoperability in Data Spaces

Governance is essential for semantic interoperability because it provides the institutional framework necessary to maintain shared meaning across decentralized systems. Within a data space, a common governance framework ensures that all participants agree on a specific data model, metadata schema, and controlled vocabularies used for discovery and access. Between different data spaces, governance interoperability is critical to avoid semantic silos by establishing agreements on how to map disparate identity regimes, data access policies, and sovereignty rules. Without this coordination, technical standards alone cannot ensure that restricted or sensitive data—such as personal health information or endangered species data—can be shared securely while preserving its original context and legal protections.

Governance interoperability for data spaces addresses the **rulebooks** that govern different data spaces, as well as the rules for data sovereignty for non-open data that must be respected within data spaces. Definitions of data spaces (there are several) highlight how, within a data space, there needs to be a common governance framework, agreed by all the participants.

⁷⁶ Data Act - <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg/2023/2854/oj/eng> (last accessed 27/12/2025)

- The Data Spaces Support Centre (DSSC)⁷⁷ defines a **data space** as: A distributed system defined by a governance framework that enables secure and trustworthy data transactions between participants while supporting trust and data sovereignty. A data space is implemented by one or more infrastructures and enables one or more use cases.
- ISO/IEC DIS 20151⁷⁸ defines a **data space** as a decentralised infrastructure for trustworthy data sharing, characterised by data sovereignty, interoperability, and common governance, where data remains with the owner and is only shared as needed under agreed-upon rules, rather than being centrally stored

These frameworks are critical for data spaces to fulfil their primary objective, enabling data providers to share restricted data with data consumers, while retaining control over how their data can be used, and maintaining confidence that data consumers will respect the rules set by each data provider.

Governance Interoperability Within Data Spaces

The governance framework is often expressed as a **rulebook** that is adopted by the data space governance authority (DSGA), the entity responsible for governance of each data space, as defined by the DSSC, as well as other groups and a common **Participation Agreement** that each participant in a data space would agree to legally.

The Trust Framework aspects of the governance framework combine contractual agreements (the Participation Agreement, as well as agreed templates for data exchange contracts) with a number of technical aspects of trust in a data space:

- Digital identity regimes that bind digital identities to legal identities,
- Mechanisms for expressing and reliably communicating claims, attributes and credentials associated with each identity,
- Data access policy and rule templates that can be selected by providers for their data, and
- Mappings between data access rules, and the claims, attributes and credentials that might be presented by data consumers to satisfy each rule, in order to unlock access to specific data.

The Eclipse Dataspace Working Group (EDWG⁷⁹) is working to specify how to express some of the above aspects of the Trust Framework, and developing software implementations able to

⁷⁷ Data Spaces Support Centre - <https://dssc.eu/space/BVE2/1071251749/Glossary> (last accessed 27/12/2025)

⁷⁸ ISO/IEC DIS 20151 - <https://www.iso.org/standard/86589.html> (last accessed 27/12/2025)

⁷⁹ Eclipse Dataspace Working Group - <https://dataspace.eclipse.org/> (last accessed 27/12/2025)

work with these aspects and technically implement data sovereignty in a scalable, interoperable way, using new generations of the Eclipse Dataspace Connector (EDC).

Governance Interoperability Between Data Spaces

The discussion above addresses governance within a Data Space, i.e. operating between participants of a given data space, with a given governance framework, rulebook, and related specifications needed for the technical implementation of data sovereignty. These interoperability artefacts do not directly address how participants in two different data spaces might interact – i.e. how a participant in one data space might be able to provide data to a participant of a separate data space, and still retain control over its use and confidence that the data consumer will respect the rules set by the data provider.

Nevertheless, such cross-data space interoperability has been identified by stakeholders and the DSSC as an important requirement, since otherwise data spaces are at risk of becoming **silos** that cannot work or talk to one another, placing burdens on both data providers (who would need to decide in which data spaces they should participate) and data consumers (who would need to participate in multiple data spaces in order to get the data they need).

Two approaches to this problem have been discussed:

1. Establish **interlinkage** connections between data spaces, giving the DSGA of each data space responsibility to provide data to other data spaces (via their own DSGAs). This approach has been proposed by the Smart Middleware Platform (SIMPL)⁸⁰ team. It would require interoperable (if not identical) identity management systems in the different data spaces, as well as requiring data providers to delegate authority (and legal responsibility) for their data to the DSGA.
2. Enable configurable connectors to work with machine-readable governance metadata from different data spaces, allowing these connectors to exchange data between data providers and data consumers in compliance with the rules set by the data provider (from one data space) and the compliance information provided by a data consumer (from another data space). This approach has been proposed by SAGE, the Green Deal Data Space. It would require agreement on how to express interoperable governance metadata, as well as creation of additional contractual agreements that could operate and be enforced between data spaces.

Governance Interoperability: Implications for EOSC

⁸⁰ SIMPL Programme - <https://simpl-programme.ec.europa.eu/> (last accessed 27/12/2025)

EOSC does not currently provide a consistent approach for data sovereignty for any restricted data. Restricted data is common in research, including:

- Personal health information
- Personal data from the social sciences and humanities
- Data linked to indigenous peoples (covered by the CARE principles)
- Sensitive data associated with environmental and climate research (water depths in coastal areas may have military/security implications, data about rivers and lakes [e.g. water levels, flow rates] are treated as confidential in many jurisdictions as well as being associated with critical infrastructure such as electric and gas power facilities)
- Information about endangered species and ethnic groups must be restricted to avoid poaching (see the Nagoya protocol) as well as ethnic violence
- Confidential economic and business data from national statistics and from companies themselves.
- Data temporarily under embargo according to specific data policies.

The mechanisms described above, being developed by Data Spaces to enable data providers to exercise their sovereignty over restricted data they might be prepared to share with others, are directly relevant to EOSC's ongoing development as a trusted source for research data of all types.

The challenges of cross data space interoperability are also mirrored in challenges faced by the EOSC Federation as it seeks to integrate capabilities from multiple EOSC Nodes into an offering that can be seamlessly navigated by researchers across Europe and globally.

3.2. Semantic Interoperability of Metadata in Data Spaces

Metadata about data assets in Data Spaces enables their discovery, access and correct/approved use.⁸¹ Governance interoperability addresses policies, rules and conditions for access and use/re-use, but semantic interoperability ensures that each phase of the research data lifecycle can be executed efficiently and unambiguously.

At the metadata layer, data products in the data spaces (e.g., datasets, computing algorithms) should be described by a range of metadata that allows the users to locate them, but also to understand precisely the coverage (spatial, temporal, domain) of the data product, among other information. All these metadata about the data products should ideally be represented in a formal way, using standard metadata schemas, including DCAT and its Application Profiles (AP). Reusing existing standards in metadata descriptions is important to enable efficient discovery of relevant research data, even across disciplines, and to avoid various semantic interoperability

⁸¹ Data Spaces Blueprint: <https://blueprint.dssc.eu/> (last accessed 16/03/2026)

issues, such as naming conflicts (e.g., one schema uses **subject** and the other, **theme**, to refer to the same concept) and data type harmonization⁸².

The DSSC Blueprint includes a specific **building block** on Data Models, recommending the use of DCAT for catalogue metadata, and encouraging each data space to select a common data model (loosely similar to metadata schema and related taxonomies and/or ontologies) for representing the data contained in the data space. This is possible for some of the common European Data Spaces, but is very difficult for data spaces such as SAGE, the Green Deal Data Space, since a broad range of disciplinary data is expected to be discoverable and usable through SAGE, and each disciplinary area itself has its own preferred data models and metadata schemas. To support its initial deployment, SAGE must accommodate a diverse array of data models, including geospatial and jurisdictional boundaries, climate, weather, and oceanography, as well as complex industrial schemas for supply chains, bills of materials, and digital product passports. Furthermore, the framework must remain extensible to incorporate future use cases involving biodiversity, environmental hazards, and evolving semantic requirements.

In the context of DCAT-3, for instance, **dcat:theme** allows us to describe the subjects of the data product, and according to DCAT, this property must be populated with terms coming from controlled vocabularies. Adopting a controlled vocabulary for indexing the values for such a field is more precise than using natural language tagging (e.g., data providers/curators using different terms to represent the same concept), and, in addition, provide valuable services within the data spaces. For instance, a taxonomy of concepts can provide an hierarchical classification that allow users to explore similar data products according to their topics, by navigating through them. In order to implement such services, formal semantic artefacts (expression used by the DSSC blueprint is **Data Models**) are needed (expressed in OWL, RDF or SKOS). Semantic Artefact Catalogues (expression used by the DSSC blueprint is **vocabulary service**), such as AgroPortal, EarthPortal, EcoPortal, OntoPortal-Astro, usually offer robust APIs to ease access to SA and selection of controlled terms. Work is in progress in the Common European Agriculture Data Space project (CEADS) to integrate into the data space components a mechanism to standardize the annotation of datasets being exchanged. This kind of integration / mechanism has been successfully implemented before in EOSC as in task 4.5 of FAIR-IMPACT⁸³.

⁸² Soares, F. M. (2025). A Semantic Interoperability Framework for Data-Centric Applications in Agriculture. [PhD Thesis - Research UT, graduation UT, University of Twente, Universidade de Sao Paulo]. University of Twente. <https://doi.org/10.3990/1.9789036567626> (last accessed 27/12/2025)

⁸³ FAIR-IMPACT - <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14917163> Aubin, S., et al. (2025). D4.6 - Use case driven validation of semantic artefact exploitation within data repositories (V1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14917164> (last accessed 27/12/2025)

The analysis of the **SIMPL framework** within the context of Semantic Interoperability reveals a significant gap between the high-level ambitions and its practical implementation as of late 2025. While SIMPL is positioned as a primary middleware for Common European Data Spaces, its approach to semantics remains largely structural rather than functional.

The SIMPL-Open⁸⁴ software stack, particularly in its Minimum Viable Product (MVP) released at the start of 2025, prioritizes technical and governance layers over semantic deep-alignment.

- SIMPL-Open specifies the use of well-known semantic standards—including DCAT-AP, SKOS, OWL, RDF, ODRL, and SHACL—to preserve meaning across systems. However, the framework remains agnostic to the internal implementation details of participants, which preserves autonomy but may result in semantic silos.
- SIMPL discusses an **interlinkage** layer using **SIMPL Open Agents** to connect disparate data spaces. In practice, current implementations (such as **Destination Earth**⁸⁵) often establish their own independent identity and semantic management regimes, making cross-data space semantic assessment difficult for restricted data.
- SIMPL relies heavily on the **Gaia-X Architecture**⁸⁶, copying its approach to governance and trust frameworks. While Gaia-X provides logic rules for machine-actionable information, its focus is primarily on **governance artefacts** rather than the harmonisation of domain-specific data schemas.

Despite the roadmap updates in mid-2025, several gaps persist regarding the actual **understanding** of data between spaces:

- Little detail exists on how compliance with a semantic "regime" is enforced beyond basic metadata registry checks.
- Different data spaces use different identity regimes (e.g., eIDAS vs. proprietary), hindering the assessment of claims and credentials across borders.
- While SIMPL supports DCAT-AP, the burden of creating crosswalks between different domain-specific metadata remains with the individual projects.
- The specifications for how SIMPL Open Agents from different spaces negotiate semantic meaning are not yet robust enough for complex data.

For EOSC to function as the Common European Data Space for Research, it cannot rely on SIMPL for semantic interoperability. The current SIMPL framework addresses discovery (via

⁸⁴ SIMPL-Open <https://simpl-programme.ec.europa.eu/dashboard/simpl-open> (last accessed 15/02/2026)

⁸⁵ Destination Earth: <https://destination-earth.eu/> (last accessed 15/02/2026)

⁸⁶ Gaia-X Architecture: <https://docs.gaia-x.eu/technical-committee/architecture-document/22.10/> (last accessed 15/02/2026)

metadata registries) and access control (via trust frameworks) but does not solve the challenge of data-level semantic integration.

3.3. Semantic Interoperability of Data in Data Spaces

At the data layer, the complexity of semantic interoperability increases. Each domain has its own data collection practices, formats, and conceptual models, which often result in datasets that do not follow a shared data model. To mitigate this heterogeneity, many research communities have developed domain-specific semantic artefacts that describe detailed descriptions of classes and attributes of data models. In the context of Data Spaces, the adoption of community-driven standards should be considered a core requirement for making datasets available. These standards prepare the ground that data is provided in machine-actionable formats, which is essential for automated processing, interoperability, and large-scale integration. When such data are aligned with recognised domain standards and expressed using controlled vocabularies, they become machine-readable by design, which is a key prerequisite for their inclusion as High-Value Datasets under EU Open Data Policy⁸⁷. High-Value Datasets are prioritised across European Data Spaces precisely because they maximize reusability, interoperability, and cross-domain value creation.

⁸⁷ European Commission. (2023, January 20). Commission Implementing Regulation (EU) 2023/138 of 21 December 2022 laying down a list of specific high-value datasets and the arrangements for their publication and re-use. Official Journal of the European Union, L 19, 43–75. https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg_impl/2023/138/oj (last accessed 27/12/2025)

4. Conclusion

This deliverable has the goal to explore common grounds in establishing semantic interoperability through existing recommendations in the upcoming EOSC Projects, in the EOSC Nodes belonging to the EOSC Federation. The basis for establishment of overall semantic interoperability among various artefacts lies in the understanding of three basic pillars of this landscape overview in the context of both EOSC Interoperable Framework and EOSC Federation of Nodes:

- 1) what recommendations are already in force,
- 2) which semantic artefacts and catalogues are already in use, and
- 3) what issues arise from the ecosystem of the data spaces.

Current recommendations coming from the previous deliverable called *Developing and implementing the semantic interoperability recommendations of the EOSC Interoperability Framework (March 2024)* are predominantly underlining semantic interoperability implementation as a challenge addressing both technical and organizational aspects. The recommendations mention the need to introduce the usage of Semantic Artefacts and Semantic Artefact Catalogues into the core infrastructure, emphasizes systematic planning and coordination instead of isolated actions, and highlights harmonization of implementation with respect to semantic interoperability. The recommendations emphasise community collaboration and a certain degree of governance. However, with the exception of explicitly mentioning the usage of FAIR Digital Objects as one of the means, it does not specify concrete ways on how to achieve this. The question remains, which semantic artefacts, catalogues, registries, crosswalks and mappings to use and how and where to specify them.

This should be summarized in a set of concrete recommendations in the 2nd upcoming deliverable of the Technical and Semantic Interoperability Task Force.

The second pillar of the analysis was understanding what specific technical implementations of semantic interoperability artefacts are already in use or being developed within the EOSC Projects, initiatives and the Nodes of the EOSC Federation. This was determined in two ways: 1) a user survey using a questionnaire sent to the projects and nodes coordinators and 2) a detailed description from several nodes on how they handle semantic interoperability. From the survey, a list of the most frequently used vocabularies and ontologies (especially those used for top-level descriptions) was obtained, as well as catalogues to register semantic artefacts. The efforts to introduce semantic interoperability in the EOSC Federation and in the EOSC projects is mostly driven bottom-up often leading to shallow descriptions. Similarly to the recommendations from the previous deliverable, there is a desire for a coordinated

implementation of a standard-based infrastructure for established and operationally-embedded semantics artefacts. Also the lack of stronger coordination and normative support is noted. Solutions may reside in stronger community collaborations, centralised infrastructure for semantic artefacts, and a sustained governance.

The feedback from the nodes revealed that implementations are based on existing community proven standards. Missing parts are often developed through projects. Despite the apparent lack of coordination between nodes, it is clear that there is interest in using existing community standards that facilitate semantic interoperability.

The Data Spaces ecosystem encounters issues with semantic interoperability on various levels: 1) governance interoperability within and between data spaces, 2) semantic interoperability of metadata and 3) semantic interoperability of data. Each of these levels defines different issues. Governance interoperability issues are in binding digital and legal entities and data access policies and in its better understanding. The semantic interoperability of metadata lies in the usage of domain-specific metadata profiles and schemes. For each Data Space it is beneficial to use metadata profiles that describe the specific domain in the best way. Problems arise as the various profiles are not easily mapped to each other. The similar problem on the larger scale also appears in the semantic interoperability of data itself, as the number of classes and properties for representation of data itself is significantly larger than classes and attributes used for their description. The important part of the solution is to register domain-specific semantic artefacts in semantic artefact catalogues and decide how to store mappings and crosswalks in a FAIR discoverable and reusable way.

This deliverable thoroughly explored the biggest challenges and requirements for ensuring semantic interoperability in EOSC and provides the basis for proposing specific recommendations. These will be addressed in the upcoming deliverable of the Semantic Interoperability working group of the Technical and Semantic Interoperability Task Force⁸⁸.

⁸⁸ Technical and Semantic Interoperability Task Force:
<https://eosc.eu/advisory-groups/technical-and-semantic-interoperability-task-force/> (last accessed 27/12/2025)

Appendix 1: Foundational Metadata Standards

These standards are frequently used across the EOSC ecosystem for describing datasets, software, and research provenance.

Standard / Specification	Description	Reference Link
DCAT / DCAT-AP	Data Catalog Vocabulary and its European Application Profile for inter-portal interoperability.	W3C DCAT / SEMIC DCAT-AP
PROV-O	The PROV Ontology for expressing provenance information in heterogeneous environments.	W3C PROV-O
Schema.org	A collaborative, community-led vocabulary for structured data on the internet.	Schema.org
SKOS	Simple Knowledge Organization System for representing thesauri, taxonomies, and classification schemes.	W3C SKOS
RO-Crate	A lightweight approach to packaging research artefacts with their metadata using Schema.org and JSON-LD.	RO-Crate
Dublin Core	A general purpose metadata vocabulary for describing resources of any type	Dublin Core

Appendix 2: Semantic Mapping and Interoperability Frameworks

Specialised frameworks designed to bridge different metadata schemas or domain-specific terminologies.

- SSSOM (Simple Standard for Sharing Ontological Mappings): A standard format for sharing and documenting mappings between different ontologies. [Reference: GitHub SSSOM](#)
- CDIF (Cross-Domain Interoperability Framework): Recommendations based on domain-neutral standards to support FAIR core functions. [Reference: CDIF Introduction](#)

- maDMP (Machine-Actionable Data Management Plans): Standards that enable the automated exchange of project information across systems. [Reference: RDA maDMP Standard](#)

Appendix 3: Definitions

- **Crosswalk schema:** Crosswalks establish relationships between elements in different models to achieve interoperability and effective data exchange in a technical way, particularly when dealing with data from various sources.
- **Data Sovereignty:** The capability of a data provider to exercise control over their data assets, including the ability to specify, communicate, and enforce the rules and conditions under which those assets are accessed and used by others.
- **Data Spaces:** A distributed system defined by a governance framework that enables secure and trustworthy data transactions between participants while supporting trust and data sovereignty. A data space is implemented by one or more infrastructures and enables one or more use cases.
- **FAIR Digital Object (FDO):** A FAIR Digital Object is an information entity composed of a persistent identifier (PID) such as a handle, like DOI, resolving to a PID Record that assigns a semantic class, along with a mechanism to retrieve its bit sequences, metadata and references to possible operations according to the FAIR principles. Editor's note: The EOSC-IF goes into some length to describe the Digital Object concept (EOSC-IF section 1.1.4) and then expand on the role of FAIR Digital Objects in EOSC (EOSC-IF section 4.1). At the same time, the activities around the FAIR Digital Objects Forum have made progress towards a formal specification for one of the potentially several interpretations of the FAIR Digital Object. Accurately summarising this body of work is beyond the scope of this document, and a recent assessment is accounted for in (Soiland-Reyes et al., 2023).
- **Knowledge Graph:** A structured representation of data and its interrelations, often using RDF (Resource Description Framework) triples, that integrates heterogeneous information sources and enables semantic search and discovery through linked metadata.
- **Machine-Actionability:** The degree to which digital objects and metadata are structured in a way that allows automated systems to process, interpret, and act upon the information without human intervention, which is a core requirement for the implementation of FAIR principles.

- **Mapping entity:** Mapping is an explicit relationship between individual concepts, terms or data elements from two semantic artefacts, metadata schemas, information systems or databases. The relationship can have different levels of complexity, ranging from a simple one-to-one equivalent relation to complex data transformations.
- **Mapping Repository (related Business Object):** The Mapping Repository component (EOSC-IF, p. 42) represents a type of service that enables interoperability by providing different types of mappings between FAIR Digital Objects. This includes different types of entity mappings or schema crosswalks, but should also expand more generally to mediation between services or transcoding across representations encoded using different combinations of data types and Semantic Objects (such as semantic artefacts and Metadata Frameworks).
- **Metadata Framework:** A structured system or schema used to consistently describe research assets, providing the conceptual rules and data types required for discovery, provenance, and management within a repository or federation.
- **Semantic Interoperability Case Study:** Description of a real-life situation where semantic artefacts are used in practice. These can be broad, covering several semantic artefacts and actors to achieve semantic interoperability.
- **Semantic Mediation:** The process of resolving semantic conflicts and bridging differences between disparate metadata schemas or vocabularies through the use of mappings and crosswalks to enable interoperability.
- **Semantic Search:** A search technique that goes beyond simple keyword matching to understand the intent and contextual meaning of a query by leveraging semantic artefacts, URIs, and knowledge graphs.
- **Semantic Artefacts:** A Semantic Artefact is a machine-actionable and readable formalisation of a conceptualisation, enabling sharing and reuse by humans and machines. These artefacts may have a broad range of formalisation, from a loose set of terms, taxonomies, thesauri to higher-order logics such as ontologies.
- **Semantic Artefacts Catalogue:** A Semantic Artefacts Catalogue is a dedicated web-based system that fosters the availability, discoverability, long-term preservation and maintenance of semantic artefacts.
- **Semantic Business Object:** Semantic Business Objects (SBOs) are *semantically relevant information objects* that are agreed upon, exchanged, and used (between service

providers/consumers) so that FAIR Digital Objects can be consistently described, understood, found, and integrated. They belong to the **semantic view** and are based on the EIRA term **business object** (information unit with technical significance).

- **Semantic Interoperability:** Semantic Interoperability enables the meaning-preserving exchange of information across machines and humans. For this purpose, the format and meaning of the exchanged data and information must be precisely specified and described (meaning preservation).
- **Semantic Interoperability Use Cases:** A usage scenario for the semantic artefacts abstracted from a case study, such that it can be generalised to other disciplines, systems or regions. Keeping track of this will support comparisons across case studies. It describes sequences of interactions between actors and semantic artefacts to achieve semantic interoperability.
- **URI (Uniform Resource Identifier):** A unique string of characters used to identify a resource (such as a concept, dataset, or organization) in a machine-readable way, serving as the foundational anchor for **actual semantics** in the EOSC ecosystem.

